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(57) Abstract :

7. ABSTRACT OF THE INVENTION The present invention provides a device and method for personalized letter writing and communication coaching for students using Machine Learning (ML) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. The system comprises an IoT-enabled device for capturing text or voice input, a cloud-based ML platform for analyzing the input using natural language processing (NLP) algorithms, and a user interface for delivering real-time feedback and progress tracking. The IoT device, equipped with sensors such as a microphone or touchscreen, collects user input and transmits it to the ML platform via a wireless connection. The ML platform evaluates the input for grammar, tone, structure, and context, generating personalized feedback and suggestions to improve communication skills. The system tracks user progress over time, adapting its coaching strategies to individual learning needs. The method involves capturing input, transmitting it for analysis, processing it with ML algorithms, and providing tailored feedback through the user interface. This invention enhances students written and verbal communication skills by offering a scalable, accessible, and adaptive learning platform suitable for educational institutions or remote use.

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